

Composition and the Stability of the Complexes of Uranyl Ion with β -Mercapto Propionic Acid

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The complexes of uranyl ion with β -mercapto-propionic acid have been investigated by potentiometric and conductometric titration techniques in aqueous 0.1 M KNO_3 . It was observed that below $p\text{H} = 6$, two complexes 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 are formed with considerable overlapping and the latter complex is more stable and pronounced. The log K values for these complexes has been computed by alternative methods at 20, 30 and 40°. The overall changes in ΔG , ΔH and ΔS accompanying the reaction have also been reported.

β -Mercapto-propionic acid (referred to herein as MPA), containing an active $-\text{SH}$ group, has been reported to form complexes with Co(III)^1 , La^2 , Ce^2 , etc. and has also been used as an analytical reagent for the detection and determination of Pd^{2+} ,³ Co^{2+} ,⁴ etc. No reference could, however, be traced out in the literature on the study of Uranyl ion complexes of MPA, their stability constants and other thermodynamic functions. Hence the present investigation has been initiated.

EXPERIMENTAL

β -Mercapto propionic-acid (99.1%) Evan's Chemetics, Inc., New York, and Anal-R (B.D.H.) reagents $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$, KNO_3 , NaOH etc., were used and their solutions prepared in doubly distilled air free conductivity water. An approximately 2×10^{-2} M solution of MPA was prepared and standardised by potentiometric titration with standard NaOH .

A Cambridge bench pattern (null deflection type) $p\text{H}$ -meter with universal glass and dip type calomel electrodes was used for $p\text{H}$ measurements and calibrated by using several solutions 10^{-2} and 10^{-3} M HClO_4 with ionic strength 0.1 M (obtained by the addition of NaClO_4). Thus the reading gave immediately concentrations and not the activities of H^+ . Before and after each series of measurements, a calibration was made. Though the meter can measure 0.01 unit of $p\text{H}$, it is supposed that with the error inherent in calibration, the ultimate error is ± 0.02 $p\text{H}$ unit. A CO_2 free nitrogen atmosphere (presaturated with 0.1 M KNO_3) was maintained above the solution throughout the titrations. All the $p\text{H}$ titrations were performed in aqueous 0.1 M KNO_3 .

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4. Edward Lyons, *Anal. Chem.*, 1955, **27**, 1813.

The experimental procedure involved a series of pH and conductometric titration of MPA with standard NaOH in the absence and presence of uranyl ion at various ligand to UO_2^{2+} ratios viz., 1 : 1, 2 : 1, 3 : 1 etc. The Calvin and Melchior's⁵ extension of Bjerrum's⁶ method was used to calculate the stability constants of the complexes formed. The data used in the determination of stability constants were taken from the region of $\text{pH} < 6$, due to the precipitation of metal hydroxide above this pH.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Stoichiometry: The stoichiometry of the reaction between uranyl ion and β -mercapto-propionic acid was determined by potentiometric and conductometric titrations of mixtures of reactants in various ratios against standard alkali (Figure-1).

Fig. 1—Potentiometric (curves 1–4) and conductometric (curves 5–7) titrations of MPA in the absence and presence of $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ with 0.1 M NaOH.

Curves 1 and 5— 3.33×10^{-3} M MPA.

Curves 2 and 6— 3.33×10^{-3} M MPA + 3.33×10^{-3} M $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$.

Curves 3 and 7— 3.33×10^{-3} M MPA + 1.66×10^{-3} M $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$.

Curve 4— 3.33×10^{-3} M MPA + 1.11×10^{-3} M $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$.

The appearance of only one inflection (Fig. 1, curve 1), after one mole of base per mole of ligand has been added, corresponds to the neutralisation of the single carboxyl hydrogen. Hence if free MPA, having two replaceable hydrogen ions is denoted as H_2SA , the reaction between 'a' (moles of NaOH added per mole of ligand) interval of 0–1 may be represented by the equation

The addition of equimolar concentration of UO_2^{2+} greatly alters the shape of the free ligand titration curve as a result of the complex formation and consequently a considerable lowering in the buffer region is indicated.

5. M. Calvin and N. C. Melchior, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3270.

6. J. Bjerrum. 'Metal Amine formation in aqueous solutions'. P Hasse and Son., Copenhagen, 1941.

When half mole of $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ is added to the ligand (Fig. 1, curve 3), the curve shows only one inflection at $a = 2$, which corresponds to the formation of $\text{UO}_2(\text{SA})_2^{2-}$ in accordance with the following equation

Since significant inflection at $a = 1.5$ is absent, the formation of UO_2SA and $\text{UO}_2(\text{SA})_2^{2-}$ should occur with considerable overlapping i.e., 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes are being formed simultaneously throughout a large portion of the titration. The inflection at $a \approx 1.66$, (Fig. 1, curve 4), when the ratio of ligand to metal has increased to 3 : 1, further confirms the formation of overlapping complexes.

Fig. 2—Potentiometric titrations of MPA in the absence and presence of $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ with 0.1 M NaOH at three different temperatures.

Curves 1, 3 and 5—3.0 ml M KNO_3 + 10.0 ml M/50 MPA (Total volume 30.0 ml) at 20, 30 and 40° respectively.

Curves 2, 4 and 6—3.0 ml M KNO_3 + 10.0 ml M/50 MPA + 1.0 ml M/50 $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (Total volume 30.0 ml) at 20, 30 and 40° respectively.

Conductometric studies : Figure 1, (curves 5, 6 and 7) represents the changes in conductance when solution of MPA was titrated against NaOH in the absence and presence of UO_2^{2+} . The breaks in titration curves suggest the simultaneous formation of UO_2SA and $\text{UO}_2(\text{SA})_2^{2-}$ complexes as obtained by potentiometric data.

It may be particularly pointed out that the polynuclear complex is not formed because of $\bar{n}$ is a function of $[\text{SA}^{2-}]$ only (which has been tested by obtaining measurements at various metal ion concentrations) and is independent of the total metal ion concentration.

Computation of stability constants: The Calvin and Melchior's⁵ extension of Bjerrum's⁶ method was used to calculate the stability constants of the complexes from

Fig. 3—Plot of $\bar{n}$ as a function of $-\log [SA^{2-}]$ at three different temperatures.

Curves—1 at 20°.

Curve—2 at 30°.

Curve—3 at 40°.

potentiometric titration data. The reaction equilibria may be represented by the following expressions :

The overall stability constant β is given by

$$\beta = \frac{[UO_2(SA)_2^{2-}]}{[UO_2^{2+}][SA^{2-}]^2} = K_1K_2 \quad (4)$$

where K_1 and K_2 are the formation constants of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes.

The procedure used for calculating the stability constants of uranyl-mercapto-propionate complexes was similar to that described in earlier publications.⁷⁻⁹ The evaluation of $\bar{n}$ was made from figure 2. At any pH, the horizontal distances between curves 1-2, 3-4 and 5-6 (corresponding to 20, 30 and 40° respectively) measure quite accurately the additional base consumed or the total number of SA^{2-} complexed. This number divided by the total UO_2^{2+} gives $\bar{n}$. At any pH, $[SA^{2-}]$ was calculated as

$$[SA^{2-}] = \frac{[H_2SA]_{Total} - [UO_2SA] - 2[UO_2(SA)_2^{2-}]}{\frac{[H^+]^2}{Ka_1 Ka_2} + \frac{[H^+]}{Ka_2} + 1} \quad (5)$$

where Ka_1 ($pKa_1 = 4.38$) and Ka_2 ($pKa_2 = 10.38$) are the first and second dissociation constants of the acid. All the quantities in equation (5) are known and thus a series of $\bar{n}$ and

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[SA²⁻] values at various pH were obtained at different temperatures and formation curves plotted (Figure 3). The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were read directly from the graph at $\bar{n}$ values of 0.5 and 1.5 respectively and were found to be 7.80 and 6.84 (at 20°); 8.05 and 7.05 (at 30°); 8.18 and 7.13 (at 40°) respectively. These values of the stability constants were further refined by the following methods: (1) Convergence formulas of successive approximation¹⁰. (2) Correction term method¹¹. and (3) Least Square treatment¹¹ and are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Method	20°			30°			40°		
	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta$	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta$	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta$
Schroder's convergence formulas	7.58	7.06	14.74	7.89	7.20	15.09	8.04	7.26	15.30
Correction term	7.61	7.10	14.71	7.82	7.22	15.04	8.04	7.28	15.32
Least Square	7.58	7.23	14.81	7.79	7.26	15.05	7.98	7.30	15.28
Mean	7.59	7.13	14.72	7.83	7.23	15.06	8.02	7.28	15.30

Thermodynamic functions: The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) on complex formation have been determined at 30° by employing the standard equations¹² as described earlier⁷⁻⁹ and found to be -20.85 K-cal/mole, -10.1 K-cal/mole and +35.5 cal/deg. respectively.

The present investigation clearly reveals the formation of UO₂SA and UO₂(SA)₂²⁻ complexes of uranyl ion with β -mercapto propionic acid. The logarithms of the stability constants were found to be 7.59 ± 0.02 and 7.13 ± 0.10 (20°); 7.83 ± 0.06 and 7.23 ± 0.03 (30°); 8.02 ± 0.04 and 7.28 ± 0.02 (40°) respectively. The values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS at 30° were found to be -20.85 K-cal/mole, -10.1 K-cal/mole and +35.5 cal/deg. respectively.

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